

Image Segmentation-Based Face Tracking on Thermal Images for Automatic Estimation of Psychophysiological States Using Facial Skin Temperature Distribution

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Abstract: In human-machine system, human and machine need to recognize each other's state with continuously, quantitatively and real-time property. Facial skin temperature could be measured with these properties by infrared thermography. The non-contact property is a great advantage in bioinstrumentation. Previous studies have been reported the availability of facial skin temperature for evaluation of psychophysiological states of a human such as stress, drowsiness and emotion. On the other hand, the development of the face detection and tracking techniques on thermal images are necessary for the automatic evaluation of psychophysiological states of a human based on facial skin temperature, measured by infrared thermography. The objective of this study is to establish the technique for face detection and tracking on thermal images. In this study, the algorithm consisting of three phases: (A) human detection based on inter-frame difference, (B) face detection based on image segmentation, and (C) face tracking based on temporal analysis, is proposed. As a result, the face region on thermal images could be detected and tracked with high precision. However, a part with low temperature such as the back of nasal and cheek was classified as a region other than a face.

Keywords: Thermal image; face tracking; image segmentation

I. INTRODUCTION

In the human-machine system, human and machine need to recognize each other's state constantly. The machine is required to recognize a human state with quantitatively and in real-time. Physiological indexes, possessing these properties, are effective as the indexes for the machine to recognize the human states. On the other hand, the measurements of physiological indexes require attaching some electrodes and sensors to a human body. In this situation, the measurements itself could induce mental and physical stress, that is, the non-contact measurements are desired at the measurement of physiological indexes. The measurement of facial skin temperature using infrared thermography, which could measure the facial temperature distribution of the objects with a non-contact property, has a great advantage at the measurement of physiological indexes. Skin temperature fluctuates with the blood flow change caused by the vasoconstriction and vasodilation based on the sympathetic nervous activity [1][2]. The nasal is

well known as the region reflecting the blood flow change based on sympathetic nervous activity because arteriovenous anastomoses, which are the bypass pathway connecting venules and arterioles, are present in large number at the nasal region as compared to the other region such as the cheek and forehead [3][4]. Additionally, a high correlation between the forehead skin temperature and tympanum temperature, which is one of the core temperatures, has been reported [5]. From these mechanisms, the previous studies have been reported that the skin temperature of a part of the region of a face such as the nasal and forehead are the effective physiological index to evaluate the psychophysiological states such as circadian rhythm [6][7], stress [8][9], drowsiness [10], and emotion [11][12]. On the other hand, the methods for evaluation of psychophysiological states using entire facial skin temperature have also been attempted [13][14]. Most of the studies of recent years focusing on facial skin temperature use thermal images (TIs), taken by infrared thermography, as the evaluation index. However, the techniques for face detection and tracking on thermal

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images are not established. The progress of analysis techniques is necessary for the satisfaction of the automatic evaluation of psychophysiological states of a human based on facial skin temperature measured as thermal images.

The algorithms of a face or object detection on color images are divided into two main approaches: supervised learning-based and segmentation-based. The methods based on neural network [15], R-CNN [16], ensemble of regression tree [17], and so on have been produced well results at the former approach. On the other hand, the huge amount of training data consisting of multiple patterns is generally required at the construction of detection models based on these algorithms. The aim of image segmentation is dividing the image to several regions based on component elements and detecting the objects. In previous studies, the face detection based on this image segmentation have been attempted [18][19]. Thermal images with the simple background can be described by a bimodal temperature distribution with background being the "cold" and humans beings the "hot" object. Therefore, the image segmentation could effective method for face detection on thermal images.

The objective of this paper is to establish the technique for face detection and tracking on thermal images. In this study, the algorithm consisting of three phases: (A) human detection based on inter-frame difference, (B) face detection based on image segmentation, and (C) face tracking based on temporal analysis, is proposed. The region, moving object existing on images, could be easily detected by the inter-frame difference. This method is considered to be more effective against thermal images than color images because thermal images are unaffected by illumination change and shadow. At the face detection, k-means clustering, which is one of the most used clustering algorithms, was used as the image segmentation. It is simple and computationally faster than the hierarchical clustering algorithm. Detected face region was tracked based on the temporal analysis.

II. APPROACH

A. Human detection

Fig. 1 shows the processing flow of proposed algorithm. Additionally, Fig. 2 shows the process of human detection based on the inter-frame difference. Thermal images basically have a bimodal temperature distribution with the background being the "cold" and

humans being the "hot". On the other hand, the object revealing the similar temperature with a human face

Fig. 1 Processing flow of proposed algorithm

Fig. 2 Process of human detection: (a) thermal image of interest: TI and (b) its previous frame: TI_b , (c) inter-frame difference image and (d) its histogram, (e) human contour, and (f) detected human region, pink rectangle.

such as a liquid display, as shown in Figs. 2 (a) and (b), could be erroneously recognized as a human face at the next face detection phase. The objective of this phase is to reduce the effect of the background by the limitation of the regions, applied to image segmentation.

Temperature fluctuations at the background are too slight compared to those due to the movement of a human. Therefore, the region of moving objects on the thermal image could be estimated by inter-frame difference represented as

$$TI_{diff}(x, y) = TI(x, y) - TI_b(x, y) \quad (1)$$

where $TI(x, y)$ is the thermal image of interest, as shown in Fig. 2 (a), $TI_b(x, y)$ is the previous frame of $TI(x, y)$, as shown in Fig. 2 (b). Temperature fluctuations due to the movement of the human being appeared in minor pixels, as shown in Figs. 2 (c) and (d). Therefore, human counter information could be detected as shown in Fig. 2 (e) by binarization based on outlier detection as

$$TI_{diff}'(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |TI_{diff}(x, y)| > \bar{x} + k\sigma \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where \bar{x} and σ are the average and standard deviation of pixels of TI_{diff} , respectively. Finally, the human region could be detected by the bounding rectangle of Fig. 2 (e), as shown in Fig. 2 (f). In Fig. 2, the liquid display revealing the similar temperature with a human face, appeared in the left side on the thermal images, was rid from the detected human region.

B. Face detection

Fig. 3 shows the process of face detection based on the image segmentation. At the application of k-means clustering, the number of clusters must be decided previously. It is considered that the human region, detected at the inter-frame phase, was divided broadly into 3 regions such as the low-temperature regions consisting of the background, the medium-temperature regions consisting of hair and clothes, and the high-temperature regions consisting of a human face. Therefore the number of clusters was set to 3. As the preprocessing, the median filter was applied to the thermal image of interest for the smoothing, as shown in Figs. 3 (a) and (b). The human region of the smoothed thermal image of interest was subjected to image segmentation based on k-means clustering. Fig. 3 (c) shows the result of k-means clustering. The centroids of each cluster were obtained as the value of temperature. The centroids of each cluster was as to table 1, that is, the regions, divided into the cluster containing of a human face, can be estimated by using centroids, as shown in Fig. 3 (d). Focusing on this figure, a part of clothes was divided to a cluster containing of a human face. A similar situation also

appears in arms uncovered with clothes, as shown in Fig. 4. Therefore, the region of a human face defines on

Fig. 3 Process of face detection: (a) detected human region on the frame of interest at the previous processing phase and (b) its smoothing image, (c) result of k-means clustering, and (d) the regions classified the cluster containing of a human face

Table. 1 The centroids of each cluster of Fig. 3 (c)

The number of cluster	Centroid
1	24.5
2	34.3
3	30.7

Fig. 4 The other situation of Fig. 3: (a) original thermal image, (b) the regions classified the cluster containing of a human face, and (c) the detected face region.

the basis of the weighting values, given based on information of the position and the size of each region of the image such as Figs. 3 (d) and 4 (b). It is considered that the region of a human face comparatively has a large size and exists at the upper area on these images compared to the other regions. The normalized values with center 0 and standard deviation 1 of the height and the size of each region in Fig. 4 (b), for instance, were as to table. 2. The region with the maximum value at the total of weighting values based on the height and the size was defined as the region of human face. From the definition, the face region was detected as the fourth object of the Fig. 4 (b), as shown in Fig. 4 (c).

C. Face tracking

When the sampling frequency is ideally large, the displacement of a human becomes very small. In this situation, it is considered that the searching area of a

Table. 2 The weighting values of each object in Fig. 4 (b) for estimation of the face region

	The number of the object in Fig. 4 (b)													
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
Height	-1.06	-0.07	-1.50	1.25	0.34	0.24	-1.51	0.53	0.37	0.80	-1.08	0.57	0.22	-0.62
Size	1.41	-0.33	-0.39	3.02	-0.33	-0.49	-0.50	-0.47	-0.42	-0.43	1.19	-0.29	-0.50	-0.47
Total	0.35	-0.40	-1.89	4.27	0.01	-0.25	-2.01	0.06	-0.05	0.37	0.11	0.29	-0.28	-1.09

human face could be confined from the next frame once the face detection was succeeded. Therefore, the searching area on the next frame of interest was determined at the around of detected face region on the current frame as to Fig. 5. Moreover, the region of a human face on the next frame was estimated by applying the face detection based on image segmentation to the defined searching area on the next frame. The searching area of a human face in the frame of interest was continuously updated based on the detected face region on the previous frame. Additionally, the face detection based on image segmentation was applied to the searching area on the frame of interest continuously. From these temporal analyses, the face tracking was attempted.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The movement of a face consists of five moving units: three patterns of rotation and horizontal movements, as shown in Fig. 6. In this paper, the applicability of the proposed algorithm was evaluated by applying the proposed algorithm to thermal videos consisting of one out of five moving units in Fig. 6. Thermal videos were measured using infrared thermography produced by FLIR System (A615). The thermal images were created at 0.05-s sampling intervals. The size of the thermal image was 640×480 pixels, and the temperature resolution was less than $0.05 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The infrared emissivity of the skin was set to $\epsilon = 0.98$.

The results are shown in Fig. 7. As a result, the face region were detected and tracked with high precision. On the other hand, a part of face region with low skin temperature such as the nasal and cheek was classified as a region other than face, as shown in the upper left of detected face region images in Fig. 7. The nasal region, classified as a region other than face, is surrounded with the detected face region. Therefore, it is considered that this region could be bridged by image

processing such as closing. On the other hand, the application of the same technique to the cheek region is

Fig. 5 The bounding rectangle of detected face region on current frame, cyan rectangle, and the searching area of face region on the next frame, pink rectangle.

Fig. 6 The moving units of a face

Fig. 7 Performance assessment at the applying the proposed algorithm to thermal videos consisting of one out of five moving units in Fig. 6

difficult. In the future study, the versatility of proposed algorithm should be evaluated by applying the proposed algorithm to thermal videos, measured by infrared thermographies with various performances, simultaneously with the solution of these problems.

III. CONCLUSION

The objective of this study was to establish the technique for face detection and tracking on thermal image. In this study, the algorithm using inter-frame difference, image segmentation and temporal analysis was proposed. As a result, the face region could be detected and tracked with high precision. On the other hand, a part of a face region with low skin temperature such as the nasal and cheek was classified as a region other than face. In the future study, the versatility of proposed algorithm should be evaluated by applying the proposed algorithm to thermal videos, measured by infrared thermographies with various performances, simultaneously with the solution of these problems.

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